

Impact of Ground Level Ozone on Agricultural Crops

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Exposure to high ozone (O₃) levels results in a significant reduction in crop yields in most crops. With the release of O₃ precursors rising in many parts of the world in the next few decades, declining yields from O₃ exposure appear to be likely to increase the challenges of feeding the global population predicted to grow and fulfill the need of population from 6 to 9 billion between 2000 and 2050. Ozone is not released directly into space. Instead, it was produced due to a complex chain reaction in the atmosphere, which involved the release of both nitrogen oxide and certain active hydrocarbons. These gases are produced from many sources, but automobiles and human activities are most important. The reaction leading to the formation of ozone favors high temperatures and intensity of light, and as a result, it is polluted nowadays. A vital feature of these ozone forms is that the high concentration of air pollution is not limited to urban or industrial areas, where nitrogen oxides and hydrocarbons are released; instead, high ozone depletion can be found in large agricultural areas, even in remote rural areas. Indeed, the ozone concentration is generally lower in cities than in the surrounding countryside. Therefore, the widespread distribution of ozone depletion in rural areas and cities is the main reason for its air pollution, affecting the agricultural crop.

According to a recent study, global yield loss is estimated between 7 to 12% in wheat. And in soybean, it is in the range of 6 to 16%, in rice 3 to 4%, and in maize it is in the range of 3 to 5%. Another study estimated that the loss of yield due to ozone in California to 19% cotton, 23% dried beans, and 24% onion. Surface O₃ significantly impacts crop yields worldwide. Yields of wheat, soybeans, and maize have been reduced by 15 percent worldwide. Global crop production is expected to increase to 50% of the population by 2050, and global crop losses amounted to 79-121 million tons by 2050 due to the depletion of the ozone layer.

Ozone can affect various levels of the organization, from cellular to individual cells to individual organs and plants and the growth of Plant communities and the ecosystem. After passing through the Pores of stomata, ozone can react with living molecules in the intercellular space and parts of extracellular fluid, which leads to the formation of secondary oxidants that can react through the cell membrane. Such reactions can be prevented or reduced by antioxidants, such as ascorbate and polyamines. Ozone depletion can cause the cells to collapse. Leading to significant foliar damage and effects on the plasma membrane can cause changes in membrane functions that can reduce photosynthetic processes in

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chloroplasts. Reduction of CO₂ is often found in leaves exposed to ozone over a long period, encouraging dark respiration likely to occur, possibly due to increased respiration associated with maintenance and repair. Decreased CO₂ assimilation and increased CO₂ respiratory loss lead to a total reduction in assimilate production and exports from source leaves. The leaves or foliage of crop plants that have been exposed to ozone for a long time, the onset of aging or maturation is usually accelerated, and the recovery of CO₂ is decreasing or may be diminished. Thus, reduced total production of assimilates and altered carbon allocation patterns result in reduced grain or seed yields. Ozone is rarely the only stress factor on plants, and a series of other factors can reverse its effects. Groundwater pressure and a lack of atmospheric vapor pressure can cause a decrease in stomatal conductance and hence in ozone Uptake, which can reduce the effects of ozone on the crop. Chemical, physiological and morphological changes in ozone-depleted leaves can also alter plant sensitivity to other pressures. There is evidence of such effects of tolerating cold stress, invasion of vegetation, and fungal infections. In the case of pests and fungi, these effects can be attributed to low ozone exposure; for example, ozone depletion of ambient concentrations has been shown to increase the activity of herbivores on Wild beans, as well as to increase fungal infestation on wheat in the low ozone concentration.

Ozone depletion is increasing due to human activities. Ozone production in the rear troposphere is limited by the release of nitrogen oxides and should increase as these emissions increase. Thus, evidence of an increase in nitrogen oxides, and an increase in nitrate concentration in developing countries, is linked to an increase in nitrogen oxides worldwide. This also Contributes to Loss in sustainable agricultural production, which causes a reduction in the food sector throughout the world. There is a great need to protect the ozone layer from collapsing, and it can be done to prevent the use of toxic gases which cause depletion of the ozone layer. These harmful gases are CFCs (chlorofluorocarbons), halogenated hydrocarbons, methyl bromide, and nitrous oxide. The other is the

reduced car use, the best option Instead of the car is a bicycle or walk and try to use local transportation to get to your destination instead to use personal transport. Do not use hazardous cleaning products locally and in your area that is harmful to the environment and the surrounding population. Many cleaning products contain harmful solvents and substances to replace these harmful substances with non-toxic products such as bicarbonate. Buy local products. This way, you get fresh products and avoid eating long-distance foods. As the travel distance increases, more nitrous oxide is produced due to how it is transported.